

CREATING A TEST FOR SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES IN THE ISPRING SUITE PROGRAM

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Annotation: In the article, it is considered that iSpring, which has a high rating among pedagogical software tools that enable the creation of multimedia electronic training courses, allows you to easily use simple presentations to create high-level training courses and conduct test controls due to its integration with the PowerPoint program.

Key words: Test, flash video, YouTube, video resource, PowerPoint, presentation, slide, single choice, multiple choice, matching, sorting, numbering, filling in the blanks, internal answers, word bank, active area.

INTRODUCTION.

We can use the iSpring program not only in the university, but also in schools. The iSpring program has several advantages.

MATERIALS AND METHODS OF RESEARCH.

iSpring Free is an authoring program that allows you to convert .ppt, .pptx, .pps, .ppsx files to Flash (.swf) and HTML5 format. Through the program, users can insert Flash-rollers and YouTube-video resources into PowerPoint presentation slides. In particular:

It allows the creation of e-learning content to be transferred to SCORM and TinCan systems, which means that it can be integrated with an optional LMS (Learning management system).

- It is possible to reduce the size of the presentation file created in PowerPoint by 97%
 - Provides protection of the presentation file created in the PowerPoint program.
- iSpring Free is absolutely free.

Figure 1.

In addition to the iSpring Free program, there is also the iSpring Suite program, which has more capabilities, and through this program, it is possible to create high-quality electronic educational content.

Using iSpring Suite tools (QuizMaker, iSpring Visuals, iSpring Dialog Trainer) it is possible to create e-textbooks, video lectures, e-control tests, questionnaires using Quiz Maker, iSpring Dialog Trainer - networked dialog e-courses and online - presentations.

Add audio and video files to the created e-course, record audio and video, synchronize with presentation slides, select various e-course players, edit, print in SCORM and Tin Can standards, export in .mp4 video format.

Figure 2. iSpring program main window.

Figure 3. iSpring work window.

The simplest and most qualitative way to check the student's knowledge is the evaluation test. The following types of test questions can be created using the iSpring Maker program:

Figure 4. The process of creating a test.

The book insert consists of 5 blocks.

Create book pages in the page block and duplicate (duplicate) created pages or delete existing ones.

The font block allows you to use different fonts and contains text editing tools. With the Risovanie block, you can put an image and a character on the first page of the book using the appropriate commands.

You can change the design and shape of the book using the design menu. There is also an option to choose a color for the book page.

In the Vid menu, you can adjust the position of the book during book editing.

Figure 5. Working in the Vid menu of the iSpring program.

CONCLUSIONS.

Using iSpringSuite tools (QuizMaker, iSpring Visuals, iSpringDialogTrainer) it is possible to create electronic textbooks, video lectures, electronic control tests, questionnaires through QuizMaker, iSpring Dialog Trainer - electronic courses with branched dialogues and online presentations.

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